

CERTAIN APPLICATIONS OF P- FUZZY SOFT STRUCTURES

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Cite This Article: S. Subramanian & E. Seethalakshmi, "Certain Applications of P-Fuzzy Soft Structures", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 294-298, 2017.

Abstract:

In this paper, we investigate the notion of P-fuzzy soft intersection groups which is a generalization of that fuzzy soft groups is provided. By introducing the notion soft fuzzy cosets, soft fuzzy quotient groups based on P-fuzzy soft intersection ideals are established. Finally, isomorphism theorems of P-fuzzy soft intersection groups related to invariant fuzzy soft sets are discussed.

Index Terms: Soft Set, Fuzzy Set, Fuzzy Soft Int-Group, Fuzzy Soft Interior Ideal, Soft Fuzzy Coset, Soft Fuzzy Quotient Group, Invariant Fuzzy Soft Set & Extended Image Set

1. Introduction:

The notion of fuzzy set was introduced by L.A.Zadeh[19], and since then this concept has been applied to various algebraic structure. Molodtsov [15] initiated the concept of soft sets that is free from the difficulties that have troubled the usual theoretical approaches. Molodtsov pointed out several directions for the applications of soft sets. Maji et.al [14] gave the operations of soft sets and their properties. Furthermore, they [9] introduced fuzzy soft sets which combine the strength of both soft sets and fuzzy sets. As a generalization of the soft set theory, the fuzzy soft set theory makes description of the objective world more realistic, practical precise in some cases, making it very promising. Since the notion of soft groups was proposed by Aktas and Cagman[2], then the soft set theory is used a new tool to discuss algebraic structures. Jun et.al [11] applied intersectional soft sets to BCK/BCI-algebras [10] an obtained many results. [18] discussed the concept of M-fuzzy subgroups. In this paper, we lay a foundation for providing a soft fuzzy algebraic tool in considering many problems that contain uncertainties. In order to provide these soft fuzzy algebraic structures, the notion of P-fuzzy soft int-groups which is a generalization of that fuzzy soft groups is provided. By introducing the notion soft fuzzy cosets, soft fuzzy quotient groups based on P-fuzzy soft int-ideals are established. Finally, isomorphism theorems of P-fuzzy soft int-groups related to invariant fuzzy soft sets are discussed.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section, we would like to recall some basic notions related to soft sets and soft int-groups. Throughout the paper, G denote arbitrary groups and e_{e_1} , and e_{e_2} are the identity elements of G, G_1 and G_2 respectively. U is an initial universe and E is a set of parameters under the conditions with respect to U. A and B are subsets of E. The set of all subsets of U is denoted by $P(U)$. Molodtsov[14] defined the concept of soft sets in the following way.

2.1 Definition: [15] A soft set f_A over U is defined as $f_A: E \rightarrow P(U)$ such that $f_A(x) = \emptyset$ if $x \notin A$.

In other words, a soft set U is a parameterized family of subsets of the universe U. For all $\epsilon \in A$ $f_A(\epsilon)$ may be considered as the set of ϵ -approximate elements of the soft set f_A . A soft set f_A over U can be presented by the set of ordered pairs:

$$f_A = \{(x, f_A(x)) / x \in E, f_A(x) \subseteq P(U)\}$$

Clearly, a soft set is not a set. For illustration, Molodtsov consider several examples in [14]. If f_A is a soft set over U, then the image of f_A is defined by $Im(f_A) = \{f_A(a) / a \in A\}$. The set of all soft sets over U will be denoted by $S(U)$. Some of the operations of soft sets are listed as follows.

2.2 Definition: [4] Let $f_A, f_B \in S(U)$. If $f_A(x) \subseteq f_B(x)$, for all $x \in E$, then f_A is called a soft subset of f_B and denoted by $f_A \subseteq f_B$. f_A and f_B are called soft equal, denoted by $f_A = f_B$ if and only if $f_A \subseteq f_B$ and $f_B \subseteq f_A$.

2.3 Definition [17] Let $f_A, f_B \in S(U)$ and χ be a function from A to B. Then the soft anti-image of f_A under χ denoted by χ_{f_A} , is a soft set over U defined by,

$$\chi_{f_A}(b) = \begin{cases} \cap \{f_A(a) / a \in A, \chi(a) = b\}, & \text{if } \chi^{-1}(b) \neq \emptyset \\ \emptyset, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for all $b \in B$. And the soft preimage of f_B under χ , denoted by $\chi^{-1}_{f_B}$, is a soft set over U defined by $\chi^{-1}_{f_B}(a) = f_B(\chi(a))$, for all $a \in A$.

Note that the concept of level sets in the fuzzy set theory, Cagman et.al [2] initiated the concept of lower inclusions soft sets which serves as a bridge between soft sets and crisp sets.

2.4 Definition: Let G be a group and $f_G \in S(U)$. Then f_G is called a P- fuzzy soft intersection groupoid over U if $f_G(pxy) \supseteq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y)$ for all $x, y \in G$. f_G is called a fuzzy soft intersection group over U if the soft intersection groupoid satisfies $f_G(px^{-1}) = f_G(x)$ for all $x \in G$.

For the sake of brevity, P- fuzzy soft intersection group is abbreviated by P-fuzzy soft int-group throughout this paper.

Example 1: Assume that $U=Z$ is the universal set and $G=Z_b$ is the subset of parameters. We define a soft set f_G by $f_G(0) = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10\}$

$f_G(1) = \{0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10\}, f_G(2) = \{1, 3, 4, 6, 7\}, f_G(3) = \{0, 2, 3, 6, 9\}, f_G(4) = \{1, 3, 4, 6, 7\}$
 $f_G(5) = \{0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10\}$. It is clear that $f_G(1 + Z) \not\supseteq f_G(1) \cap f_G(Z)$, implying f_G is not a soft int-group over U .

2.5 Lemma: Let f_G be a fuzzy soft set over U . If f_G is a P-fuzzy soft int-group of G , then

$$(i) (f_G(px^{-1})) \geq f_G(x). (ii) f_G(px^{-1}) \geq f_G(e) \text{ for all } x \in G.$$

Proof: (i) Assume that f_G is a P-fuzzy soft int-group of G . Then for all $x \in G$, we get that

$$(f_G(px^{-1})) = (f_G(px^{-1}) \geq (f_G((px^{-1})^{-1})) = (f_G(x)), (ii) It is straight forward.$$

2.6 Lemma: Let f_G be a fuzzy soft set over U . If f_G is a P-fuzzy soft int-group of G , then

$$(i) (f_G(e) \geq f_G(x) (ii) f_G(e.1) \geq f_G(x) \text{ for all } x \in G.$$

Proof: (i) Assume that f_G is a P-fuzzy soft int-group of G . Then for all $x \in G$, we get that

$$(i) (f_G(e) = (f_G(xx^{-1}) \geq (f_G(x) \cap f_G(x^{-1})) = ((f_G(x) \cap (f_G(x^{-1}) \geq (f_G(x)) \text{ (By Lemma:1)}$$

(ii) It is straight forward.

2.7 Definition: Let f_G be a fuzzy soft set over U . f_G is called a P-fuzzy soft int-group of U if

$$(i) f_G(pxy) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y) (ii) f_G(px^{-1}) = f_G(x) \text{ For all } x, y \in G.$$

Example 2: Let $Z/(3) = \{\bar{0}, \bar{1}, \bar{2}\}$ be a modulo 3 residue class group, $A = \{\lambda_1, \lambda_2\}$. Define a fuzzy soft set (F, A) over $\langle Z/(3), + \rangle$ as ; $F(\lambda_1)(\bar{0})=0.3, F(\lambda_1)(\bar{1})=0.6, F(\lambda_1)(\bar{2})=0.8, F(\lambda_2)(\bar{0})=0.4,$

$F(\lambda_2)(\bar{1})=0.5, F(\lambda_2)(\bar{2})=0.7$. It is easy verify that $F(\lambda_1), F(\lambda_2)$ are fuzzy subgroups of $\langle Z/(3), + \rangle$. Therefore (F, A) is a M-fuzzy soft int-groups over $\langle Z/(3), + \rangle$.

Example 3: Let $G = \{e, x, y, z\}$ be the group with the binary operation defined below.

*	e	x	y	z
e	e	x	y	z
x	x	z	e	y
y	y	e	z	x
z	z	y	x	e

Let $A = \{h_1, h_2\}$ be the set of parameters. For each parameter $h_1 \in A, F(h_1): G \rightarrow [0,1]$. For each parameter we define $F(h_1) = \{ \langle e, 0.6 \rangle, \langle x, 0.75 \rangle, \langle y, 0.62 \rangle, \langle z, 0.31 \rangle \}, F(h_2) = \{ \langle e, 0.77 \rangle, \langle x, 0.88 \rangle, \langle y, 0.92 \rangle, \langle z, 0.7 \rangle \}$. Here (F, A) is fuzzy soft int-group. Combining lemma: 2 and Definition 2.4, we obtain the following characterization of P-fuzzy soft int-groups.

2.8 Theorem: A fuzzy soft set f_G over U is a P-fuzzy soft int-group over U if and only if

$$f_G(pxy^{-1}) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y) \text{ for all } x, y \in G.$$

Proof: Suppose that f_G is a P-fuzzy soft int-group over U . Then

$$f_G(pxy^{-1}) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y^{-1}) = f_G(x) \cap f_G(y) \text{ for all } x, y \in G.$$

Conversely, suppose that $f_G(pxy^{-1}) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y)$ for all $x, y \in G$.

First, choosing $x=e$ yields $f_G(py^{-1}) \geq f_G(y)$. Thus,

$$f_G(py) = f_G((py^{-1})^{-1}) \geq f_G(y^{-1}). \text{ Hence } f_G(y) = f_G(y^{-1}). \text{ Secondly}$$

$f_G(pxy) = f_G(px(y^{-1})^{-1}) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y^{-1}) = f_G(x) \cap f_G(y)$. Therefore f_G is a P-fuzzy soft int-group over U .

2.9 Theorem: Let f_G over U is a P-fuzzy soft int-group over U and $x \in G$. Then

$$f_G(pxy) \geq f_G(y) \text{ for all } y \in G \text{ if and only if } f_G(px) = f_G(e).$$

Proof: Let $f_G(pxy) \geq f_G(y)$ for all $y \in G$.

Choosing $y = e$ yields $f_G(x) \geq f_G(e)$, thus by lemma:2, $f_G(x) = f_G(e)$.

Conversely, let $f_G(x) = f_G(e)$. Then $f_G(pxy) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y) = f_G(e) \cap f_G(y) = f_G(y)$.

2.10 Theorem: Let f_G and f_H be P-fuzzy soft int-group over U . Then $f_G \wedge f_H$ is also a P-fuzzy soft int-group over U .

Proof: Let $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in G \times H$. Then

$$f_{G \wedge H}((x_1, y_1)(x_2, y_2)^{-1}) = f_{G \wedge H}(x_1x_2^{-1}, y_1y_2^{-1}) = f_G(x_1x_2^{-1}) \cap f_H(y_1y_2^{-1}) \geq (f_G(x_1) \cap f_G(x_2)) \cap (f_H(y_1) \cap f_H(y_2)) = (f_G(x_1) \cap f_H(y_1)) \cap (f_G(x_2) \cap f_H(y_2)) = f_{G \wedge H}(x_1, y_1) \cap f_{G \wedge H}(x_2, y_2). \text{ Therefore, } f_G \wedge f_H \text{ is a P-fuzzy soft int-group over } U. \text{ Note that } f_G \vee f_H \text{ is not a P-fuzzy soft int-group over } U.$$

2.11 Definition: Let $f_A, f_B \in S(U)$. Then, \wedge -Product and \vee -Sum of f_A and f_B , denoted by $f_A \wedge f_B$ and $f_A \vee f_B$, are defined by $f_{A \wedge B}(x, y) = f_A(x) \cap f_B(y), f_{A \vee B}(x, y) = f_A(x) \cup f_B(y)$ for all $x, y \in E$ respectively.

2.12 Definition: Let f_G and f_H be P-fuzzy soft int-groups over U . Then, the product of soft int-groups f_G and f_H is defined as $f_G \times f_H = f_{G \times H}$ where

$$f_{G \times H}(x, y) \wedge \alpha = f_G(x) \times f_H(y) \cup \beta \text{ for all } (x, y) \in G \times H.$$

2.13 Theorem: If f_G and f_H be P-fuzzy soft int-groups over U , then so is $f_G \times f_H$ over $U \times U$.

Proof: By definition: 2.4, let $f_G \times f_H = f_{G \times H}$ where

$$f_{G \times H}(x, y) = f_G(x) \times f_H(y) \text{ for all } (x, y) \in G \times H.$$

Then for all $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in G \times H$,

$f_{G \times H} ((x_1, y_1) (x_2, y_2)^{-1}) = f_{G \times H} (x_1 x_2^{-1}, y_1 y_2^{-1}) = f_G (x_1 x_2^{-1}) \times f_H (y_1 y_2^{-1}) \geq (f_G(x_1) \cap f_G(x_2)) \times (f_H(y_1) \cap f_H(y_2)) = (f_G(x_1) \times f_H(y_1)) \cap (f_G(x_2) \times f_H(y_2)) = f_{G \times H} (x_1, y_1) \cap f_{G \times H} (x_2, y_2)$. Hence, $f_G \times f_H = f_{G \times H}$ is fuzzy soft int-groups over $U \times U$.

2.14 Theorem: Let f_H be P-fuzzy soft int-group over U and h be a homomorphism from G to H . Then $h^{-1}(f_H)$ is P-fuzzy soft int-group over U .

Proof: Let $x, y \in G$. Then,

$$h^{-1}(f_H)(xy) = f_H(h(xy)) = f_H(h(x)h(y)) \geq f_H(h(x)) \cap f_H(h(y)) = h^{-1}(f_H)(x) \cap h^{-1}(f_H)(y) .\text{Also,}$$

$$h^{-1}(f_H)(x^{-1}) = f_H(h(x^{-1})) = f_H((h(x))^{-1}) = f_H(h(x)) = h^{-1}(f_H)(x)$$

Hence, $h^{-1}(f_H)$ is P-fuzzy soft int-group over U .

2.15 Definition: A fuzzy soft set f_G over U is called P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G if it satisfies $f_G(xy) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y)$, $f_G(xwy) \geq f_G(x)$ for all $x, y, w \in G$.

2.16 Definition: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G ; then $E \text{ Im}(f_G)$ is called the extended image set of f_G , where $E \text{ Im}(f_G) = \text{Im}(f_G) \cup (\alpha, \beta)$. Now we characterize P-fuzzy soft int-ideals by upper inclusion.

2.17 Theorem: Let f_G be a fuzzy soft set over U and $E \text{ Im}(f_G)$ a totally order set in inclusion. Then f_G is a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G if and only if $\cup(f_G: \lambda)$ is an ideal of G , whenever it is non empty, for each $\lambda \subseteq U$ where $\beta \leq \lambda < \alpha$.

Proof: Assume that f_G is a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G and $\cup(f_G: \lambda)$ is non empty.

It is sufficient to show that $x y \in \cup(f_G: \lambda)$. Let $x, y \in \cup(f_G: \lambda)$ it follows that $f_G(x) \geq \lambda$ and $f_G(y) \geq \lambda$. Since f_G is a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G and $E \text{ Im}(f_G)$ a totally order set, then

$$f_G(xy) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y) \geq \lambda \cup \lambda \cup \lambda = \lambda < \alpha,$$

$$f_G(xwy) \geq f_G(x) \geq \lambda \cup \lambda = \lambda < \alpha.$$

And thus $f_G(xy) \geq \alpha$. Hence $x y \in \cup(f_G: \lambda)$. Therefore $\cup(f_G: \lambda)$ is an ideal of G .

Conversely, assume that $\cup(f_G: \lambda)$ is an ideal of G , whenever it is non empty, for each

$\lambda \subseteq U$ where $\beta \leq \lambda < \alpha$. Suppose that $f_G(xy) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y)$ does not holds for some $x, y \in G$; then there exists $x_0, y_0 \in G$ such that $f_G(x_0 y_0) \leq \lambda = (f_G(x_0) \cap f_G(y_0))$. There fore $f_G(x_0) \cap f_G(y_0) \supseteq \lambda$; that is $x_0 y_0 \notin \cup(f_G: \lambda)$ which is contradiction. Hence

$f_G(xy) \geq f_G(x) \cap f_G(y)$, for all $x, y \in R$. Similarly, we can prove that $f_G(xwy) \geq f_G(x)$ for all $x, y, w \in G$. Thus, f_G is a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G .

2.18 Theorem: Let f_G be a fuzzy soft set over U and χ is a group homomorphism from G_1 to G_2 . If f_{G_1} is a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G_2 , then $\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})$ is a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G_1 .

Proof: Let $x_1, x_2 \in G_1$. Then

$$\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})(x_1 x_2) = f_{G_2}(\chi(x_1 x_2)) = f_{G_2}(\chi(x_1) \cdot \chi(x_2)) \geq f_{G_2}(\chi(x_1)) \cap f_{G_2}(\chi(x_2)) = \chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})(x_1) \cap \chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})(x_2).$$

Moreover, we have

$$\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})(x_1 w x_2) = f_{G_2}(\chi(x_1 w x_2)) = f_{G_2}(\chi(x_1) \cdot \chi(w) \cdot \chi(x_2)) \geq (f_{G_2}(\chi(x_1))) = \chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})(x_1).$$

Hence $\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})$ is P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G_1 .

2.19 Theorem: Let f_{G_1} be a fuzzy soft set over U and χ a group epimorphism from G_1 to G_2 . If f_{G_1} is a P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G_1 , then $\chi(f_{G_1})$ is P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G_2 and $(\chi(f_{G_1}))(e_2) = (f_{G_1})(e_1)$.

Proof: Let $y_1, y_2 \in G_2$ and f_{G_1} is a (P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G_1 . Since χ is a group epimorphism from G_1 to G_2 , then $\chi^{-1}(y_1) \neq \emptyset$ and $\chi^{-1}(y_2) \neq \emptyset$. And thus, there exist

$x_1, x_2 \in G_1$ such that $\chi(x_1) = y_1, \chi(x_2) = y_2$. There fore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(f_{G_1})(y_1 y_2) &= \cap \{f_{G_1}(x_1 x_2) / \chi(x_1 x_2) = y_1 y_2\} = \cap \{f_{G_1}(x_1 x_2) / \chi(x_1 x_2) = y_1 y_2\} \\ &\geq \cap \{f_{G_1}(x_1) \cap f_{G_1}(x_2) / \chi(x_1) = y_1, \chi(x_2) = y_2\} = \cap \{f_{G_1}(x_1) / \chi(x_1) = y_1\} \cap \{f_{G_1}(x_2) / \chi(x_2) = y_2\} = \chi \\ &\quad (f_{G_1})(y_1) \cap \chi(f_{G_1})(y_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(f_{G_1})(y_1 w y_2) &= \cap \{f_{G_1}(y_1 w y_2) / \chi(x_1 w x_2) = y_1 w y_2\} = \cap \{f_{G_1}(y_1 w y_2) / \chi(x_1 w x_2) = y_1 w y_2\} \\ &\geq \cap \{f_{G_1}(y_1) / \chi(x_1) = y_1\} = \cap \{f_{G_1}(x_1) / \chi(x_1) = y_1\} = \chi(f_{G_1})(y_1) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\chi(f_{G_1})$ is P-fuzzy soft interior ideal of G_2 . by lemma: 2, we have

$$(\chi(f_{G_1}))(e_2) = (\cap \{f_{G_1}(x) / x \in G_1, \chi(x) = e_2\}) = \cap \{(f_{G_1}(x)) / x \in G_1, \chi(x) = e_2\} = (f_{G_1})(e_1).$$

3. Soft Version Fuzzy Quotient Groups:

The main purpose of this section is to give an approach for constructing soft fuzzy quotient groups based on P-fuzzy soft interior ideals. Such approaches involve the concept of soft fuzzy cosets. In addition, some simple characterizations of soft fuzzy cosets are presented.

3.1 Definition: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft int-group of G over U and $g \in G$. Then, a soft fuzzy coset $g \oplus f_G$ of f_G is defined by $(g \oplus f_G)(x) = (f_G(x - g))$, for all $x \in G$.

3.2 Theorem: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft int-group of G over U and $a, b \in G$. Then $(f_G(ab)) = (f_G(e))$ if and only if $(f_G(ba)) = (f_G(e))$.

Proof: Suppose that $(f_G(ba)) = (f_G(e))$

Since f_G is M-fuzzy soft int-group, then $(f_G(ab) = (f_G(ab) \geq ((f_G(ba) = (f_G(ba) = (f_G(e)$
 By lemma:2, we have, $(f_G(e) \geq (f_G(ab)$. Thus, $(f_G(ab) = (f_G(e)$.

Conversely, assume that $(f_G(ab) = (f_G(e)$. We can prove that $(f_G(ba) = (f_G(e)$ in a similar way.

3.3 Proposition: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft int-group of G over U and $a, b \in G$. Then $a \oplus f_G = b \oplus f_G$ if and only if $(f_G(ab) = (f_G(e)$.

Proof: Suppose that $(f_G(ab) = (f_G(e)$, Then $(b \oplus f_G)(x) = (f_G(xb) = (f_G(xaa^{-1}b) = (f_G(xaa^{-1}b) \geq ((f_G(xa) \cap f_G(a^{-1}b) = ((f_G(xa) \cap (f_G(a^{-1}b) = ((f_G(xa) \cap ((f_G(e)) \geq (f_G(xa) = (a \oplus f_G)(x)$ for all $x \in G$.

Therefore $b \oplus f_G \geq a \oplus f_G$. Similarly we can show that $a \oplus f_G \geq b \oplus f_G$. Hence $b \oplus f_G = a \oplus f_G$.

Conversely, assume that $a \oplus f_G = b \oplus f_G$. It follows that $(f_G(ab) = (b \oplus f_G)(a) = (a \oplus f_G)(a) = (f_G(e)$.

Based on the above proposition, we give a property related to soft fuzzy cosets as follows.

3.4 Proposition: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft int-ideal over U and $a, b, x, y \in G$. If $x \oplus f_G = a \oplus f_G, y \oplus f_G = b \oplus f_G$, then $xy \oplus f_G = ab \oplus f_G, xwy \oplus f_G = a \oplus f_G$.

Proof: Suppose $x \oplus f_G = a \oplus f_G, y \oplus f_G = b \oplus f_G$.

Then, $f_G(xa) = (f_G(e)$ and $(f_G(yb) = (f_G(e)$, by proposition 3.3. Since f_G is a M-fuzzy soft int-ideal, then

$(f_G((xyab)) = (f_G((xa.yb) = (f_G((xa.yb)) \geq ((f_G(xa) \cap f_G(yb) = (f_G(xa) \cap (f_G(yb) = (f_G(e)$

On the other hand, it follows from lemma:2 that $(f_G(e) \geq (f_G((xyab))$

Hence $(f_G((xyab)) = (f_G(e)$, and so $xy \oplus f_G = ab \oplus f_G$.

More over $(f_G((xwyab)) = (f_G((xawy.aywb) = (f_G((xay) = f_G \geq ((f_G(xa) = (f_G(xa) = (f_G(e)$

According to lemma :2, we get that $f_G(e) \geq f_G((xwyab))$

Therefore, $(f_G(e) \geq f_G((xyab))$; that is $xy \oplus f_G = ab \oplus f_G$.

In view of proposition 3.3, we have the following result.

3.5 Proposition: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft int-ideal over U . Then $(G/f_G, .)$ is a group, where $G/f_G \triangleq \{ a \oplus f_G / a \in G \}$, $(x \oplus f_G) (y \oplus f_G) \triangleq xy \oplus f_G$, and $(x \oplus f_G)w (y \oplus f_G) \triangleq xy \oplus f_G$, for all $x, y \in G$.

Proof: It is straight forward.

3.6 Definition: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft int-ideal over U . Then $(G/f_G, .)$ is called a soft fuzzy quotient group.

3.7 Theorem: Let f_G be a P-fuzzy soft int-ideal over U . Then $G/f_G^* \cong G/f_G$.

Proof: Assume that $h: G \rightarrow G/f_G$ such that $h(x) = x \oplus f_G$, for all $x \in G$. It is easy to see that h is a surjective homomorphism from G to G/f_G .

Since $\text{Ker}(h) = \{ x \in G / h(x) = e \oplus f_G \} = \{ x \in G / x \oplus f_G = e \oplus f_G \} = \{ x \in G / (f_G(x) = f_G(e) = f_G^* \}$. Therefore, $G/f_G^* \cong G/f_G$.

3.8 Definition: Let $\chi: G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be a group homomorphism. A fuzzy soft set of f_{G_1} over U is called invariant fuzzy soft set with respect to χ if $\chi(x_1) = \chi(x_2)$ implies $f_{G_1}(x_1) = f_{G_1}(x_2)$ for all $x_1, x_2 \in G_1$.

Next, we establish isomorphism theorems on P-fuzzy soft int-groups.

3.9 Theorem: Let $\chi: G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be an epimorphism and let P-fuzzy soft int-ideal f_{G_1} be a invariant fuzzy soft set with respect to χ . Then $G_1/f_{G_1} \cong G_2/\chi(f_{G_1})$.

Proof: Let $\chi: G_1 \rightarrow G_2/\chi(f_{G_1})$ be a mapping such that $\chi(x) = \chi(x) \oplus f_{G_1}$, for all $x \in G_1$. Obviously, χ is an epimorphism. Since f_{G_1} be a invariant fuzzy soft set with respect to χ ,

$\text{Ker}(\chi) = \{ x \in G_1 / \chi(x) = e_2 \oplus \chi(f_{G_1}) \} = \{ x \in G_1 / \chi(x) \oplus \chi(f_{G_1}) = e_2 \oplus \chi(f_{G_1}) \}$

$= \{ x \in G_1 / \chi(f_{G_1})(\chi(x)) = \{ \chi(f_{G_1})(e_2) = \{ x \in G_1 / x \oplus f_{G_1} = e_1 \oplus f_{G_1} \} = f_{G_1}^*$

Therefore, $G_1/f_{G_1}^* \cong G_2/\chi(f_{G_1})$. By theorem: 3.2 we have $G_1/f_{G_1}^* \cong G_1/f_{G_1}$. Hence $G_1/f_{G_1} \cong G_2/\chi(f_{G_1})$.

3.10 Proposition: Let $\chi: G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ be an epimorphism and let P-fuzzy soft int-ideal f_{G_2} be a invariant fuzzy soft set with respect to χ . Then $G_1/\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2}) \cong G_2/f_{G_2}$.

Proof: It follows from the theorem 3.2 and proposition 3.4 that $\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})$ is a P-fuzzy soft int-ideal of G_1 and $\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})$ is a invariant fuzzy soft set with respect to χ . Since χ is an epimorphism, then $\chi(\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2})) = f_{G_2}$, we get $G_1/\chi^{-1}(f_{G_2}) \cong G_2/f_{G_2}$.

Conclusion:

In this paper, using fuzzy soft sets and intersection of sets, we have defined P-fuzzy soft int-group that is new type of fuzzy soft group on a fuzzy soft set and then make theoretical studies of P-fuzzy soft int-groups and P-fuzzy soft int-ideals in more detail and improved several results. We have focused on P-fuzzy soft int-groups and P-fuzzy soft int-ideals, anti-image of fuzzy soft set and investigate these notions with respect to P-fuzzy soft int-groups and P-fuzzy soft int-ideals.

Future Work:

To extend our work, further research can be done to study the properties of fuzzy soft substructures in other algebraic structures such as modules, rings and fields.

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